

Article: A HISTORICAL REVIEW OF JEWS AND THE PROPHETS' KILLINGS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CURRENT MUSLIM GENOCIDE IN GAZA

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ABSTRACT

The Holy Qur'an describes several terrible Jewish crimes, the most heinous of which being the murder of the Prophets. The claim of the Holy Qur'an is supported and confirmed by the pages of Jewish history itself, where the Jewish nation is seen step by step in the blood of innocent and great people like the Prophets. When Prophet Jesus (peace be upon him) was brought into the world, the Jews' rebelliousness reached its pinnacle, yet they got unable to murder him due to his ascent to heaven, however, two of his contemporary prophets, Zechariah and John had been killed by Jewish.

After the establishment of occupied Israel in 1948, this Jewish nature has once again been fully revealed to the world that the killers of the prophets are now massacring innocent Palestinians and the number of innocent people killed in the recent war has exceeded twenty thousand. This article examines the same historical fact that the persecution of Palestinian Muslims for the past seventy-five years and the current massacre in Gaza is not an ordinary thing, but that it is a part of Jewish nature because this nation never hesitated to kill the prophets so how can they have mercy on followers of these prophets.

Keywords: Prophets, Jewish, Israel, murders, Muslim genocide.

Introduction:

Both the Holy Quran and the Holy Bible agree that the Jews have been unjustly killing the Prophets of Allah.¹ It is because of the killing of these innocent saints that Allah's punishment came down on them many times in the form of slavery, killing and looting of different nations and despite being given many opportunities to repent by Allah Almighty, they did not repent. According to prophecy by prophet Jesus, the kingdom of God was taken away from them forever² and according to the Holy Qur'an, these people became annoyed in the sight of Allah. This attitude of the Jews did not change despite going into Babylonian captivity and returning from there. They even tried to kill God's Prophet Jesus (peace be upon him), but this time Allah blocked all their plans and Jesus (peace be upon him) was lifted to the heaven.³

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Murder of hundreds of prophets:

In the Torah, the first mention of "the innocent murder of the Prophets" is found in the Book of Kings, where Jezebel, the wife of Ahab, the king of Israel, martyred a large number of prophets. Jezebel was a priestess of the god Baal and After marrying King Ahab of Israel, she strongly urged the king to allow Baal worship in Israel. ⁴ Jezebel's idolatrous nature can be inferred from the fact that her name (Ez-baal) also meant "where Baal is".⁵ Something along these lines regarding this massacre appears in the Bible.

"While Jezebel was killing off the Lord's prophets, Obadiah had taken a hundred prophets and hidden them in two caves, fifty in each, and had supplied them with food and water.)"⁶

"Haven't you heard, my lord, what I did while Jezebel was killing the prophets of the Lord? I hid a hundred of the Lord's prophets in two caves, fifty in each, and supplied them with food and water."⁷

At that time, Prophet Obadiah (Abdullah) took a hundred prophets with him and quietly hid them in a cave. We do not know the names of these prophets, but it is clear from the statement of the Holy Bible that this group of saints were part of the Jewish society and were regularly living with their wives and children. This is explained in the Book of Sultans, where the wife of an unknown prophet comes to Hazrat Elisha with a complain.⁸ These people were trying their best to bring the foolish people of Baal worshipers to the right path.

Attempt to murder Prophet Elijah:

Jezebel did not just kill a large number of prophets, but she also threatened to kill Elijah⁹ And his son-in-law Jehoram tried to threaten Elijah's disciple Prophet Elisha by showing his intention to kill him. Jehoram's father's name was Jehoshaphat, and he married Athaliah, the daughter of Ahab and Jezebel, who led him astray from the good ways of his father, so he killed six of his brothers and forced the people into idolatry. According to the prophecy of Prophet Ilyas (peace be upon him), he suffered from a curable disease and died of that disease.¹⁰ Therefore none of these two threats proved effective, nor could he act on it. At the other hand, due to crimes of supporting the god Baal, being its priests and persecuting and killing God's prophet, God Almighty punished Jezebel that dogs would eat flesh of Jezebel

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near the wall of Jezreel.¹¹ All this incident shows that Jezebel regularly took action against the entire Jewish society where a large number of prophets lived and all these people were involved in the reformation of the Israelites.

Murder of Prophet Zacharias:

At the same time, King Jehoash of Judea in the separate kingdom of Judah ordered the killing of Zacharias bin Yehuda. Jehoash was the son of King Ahaziah and became the king of Jehovah's kingdom at the age of seven. Under the influence of Priest Jehoiada, he restored the temple and abolished the worship of Baal. After Jehoiada's death, Jehoash again went astray and resumed idolatry. Prophet Zacharias raised his voice against the king for his idolatry, so he was martyred by pelting stones inside and did not even care about the sanctity of God's house.

“They abandoned the temple of the LORD, the God of their ancestors, and worshiped Asherah poles and idols. Because of their guilt, God’s anger came on Judah and Jerusalem. Although the LORD sent prophets to the people to bring them back to him, and though they testified against them, they would not listen. Then the Spirit of God came on Zechariah son of Jehoiada the priest. He stood before the people and said, “This is what God says: ‘Why do you disobey the LORD’s commands? You will not prosper. Because you have forsaken the LORD, he has forsaken you.’” But they plotted against him, and by order of the king they stoned him to death in the courtyard of the LORD’s temple.”¹²

Jehoash, the king of Judah, was righteous at first, but later he was overcome by Satan so he martyred the prophet priding of his power. In the Gospel of Matthew, Jesus Christ has also mentioned the killing of Zacharias that the Jews are responsible for the blood of Abel to Zacharias.¹³ The Hasmonean kings (who were not descendants of the kings of Judah) built a huge memorial tomb in the Kidron Valley outside of Jerusalem in memory of Hazrat Zechariah.¹⁴

Before the Babylonian exile and the end of Judah's kingdom, Jehoiakim, the king of Judah, killed Prophet Uriah, son of Shemaiah, just because he had predicted the fall of

Jehoiakim's kingdom and the end soon. He killed himself with his sword and also desecrated his body. This whole incident is mentioned in the book of Jeremiah.

“Now Uriah son of Shemaiah from Kiriath Jearim was another man who prophesied in the name of the LORD; he prophesied the same things against this city and this land as Jeremiah did. When King Jehoiakim and all his officers and officials heard his words, the king was determined to put him to death. But Uriah heard of it and fled in fear to Egypt. ²² King Jehoiakim, however, sent Elnathan son of Akbor to Egypt, along with some other men. ²³ They brought Uriah out of Egypt and took him to King Jehoiakim, who had him struck down with a sword and his body thrown into the burial place of the common people.”¹⁵

Attempt to kill Prophet Jeremiah:

Later, during the reign of King Zedekiah, his courtiers advised the king to kill Prophet Jeremiah because it was not in the best interest of the people, but the king did not listen to their words and defended Prophet Jeremiah. King Zedekiah, was a very weak ruler who was called a puppet ruler. His nobles knew that he was not able to stop them, so these wicked people took action against Prophet Jeremiah and captured him in the courtyard of a prison. Put it inside the tank. Since it was not rainy season, the reservoir was only full of mud, so they drowned Jeremiah in the mud. ¹⁶

After a period of time, when the Israelites returned from Babylonian exile, the public martyrdom of Prophet Zechariah and the brutal massacre of the Prophets by Jezebel have declared the crimes of the misguided kings of Israel and their advisors who had committed to misguide Israel and attributed these events to the captivity of the Israelites.¹⁷

Prophet Elijah clearly declared the actions of Jezebel and Ahab to be the actions of the entire nation of Israel because no Israeli raised his voice against this oppression. As stated in the Holy Book.

“And the word of the LORD came to him: “What are you doing here, Elijah?” He replied, “I have been very zealous for the LORD God Almighty. The Israelites have rejected your covenant, torn down your altars, and

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put your prophets to death with the sword. I am the only one left, and now they are trying to kill me too.”¹⁸

New Testament of prophets’ killing:

In the New Testament, Jesus describes the intense tension between Jerusalem's rulers and God's messengers.

“Jerusalem, Jerusalem, you who kill the prophets and stone those sent to you, how often I have longed to gather your children together, as a hen gathers her chicks under her wings, and you were not willing.”¹⁹

The New Testament also mentions the martyrdom of Prophet Zechariah and the commemorative tomb built by the Hasmoneans, which was later built by the Herodians. The New Testament includes all the sinful kings of Israel rebuked by Prophet Jesus for building and decorating the tombs of the prophets, saying that if we had been in the days of our fathers, we would not partake of the blood of the prophets. In this way, they testify about themselves that they are the children of the killers of the prophets, then how will you be saved from the punishment of hell? Prophets and wise men come to you, but you kill them and flog them in the synagogues²⁰

According to ancient Christian traditions, the father of Prophet Yahya (peace be upon him) Prophet Zacharias was martyred when the massacre of innocent children was going on under the orders of Herod. Prophet Zakariya (AS) hid his son and even when the Jews inquired, he was martyred if he did not tell them the hidden place.²¹

However, there is no historical evidence that Herod issued any order for the massacre of infants, but there are indications that many people, were killed by his orders, even his sons. According to the New Testament, Pilate the governor ordered Jesus to be flogged and washed his hands of his blood to absolve himself of the guilt, whereupon the crowd shouted that his blood be on us and on the necks of our descendants.²²

“When Pilate saw that he was getting nowhere, but that instead an uproar was starting, he took water and washed his hands in front of the crowd. “I am innocent of this man’s blood,” he said. “It is your

*responsibility!" And all the people answered and said, His blood be on us, and on our children."*²³

At this point, the Pharisees were completely absent, but the high priest of the Sadducees, the crowd of elderly Jews represented the Israelites as a nation on this occasion, and they were ready to take the blame for the blood of Jesus upon themselves. The Sadducees were so violent in this matter that they allegedly wanted to punish Jesus according to the Gospels, but after Jesus, they did not treat Jesus' brother, Saint James, but threw him from the roof of the temple and killed him.²⁴

The murder of Prophet John the Baptist:

In addition to the four Gospels, Saint Paul also wrote in his letter that the Jews were experts in killing prophets. As he wrote;

*"For ye, brethren became imitators of the churches of God which are in Judaea in Christ Jesus: for ye also suffered the same things of your own countrymen, even as they did of the Jews; who both killed the Lord Jesus and the prophets, and drove out us, and please not God, and are contrary to all men."*²⁵

The prominent Prophet of the New Testament, John the Baptist (Prophet Yahya, peace be upon him), was also martyred by Jews but Gospel writers have turned this matter towards Idumaeen rulers of Judea. According to the Gospel, Herod Antipas beheaded Prophet John Baptist because he had married his brother's wife, and John the Baptist (A.S) reprimanded him for this and severely criticized him.

*"Now Herod had arrested John and bound him and put him in prison because of Herodias, his brother Philip's wife, for John had been saying to him: "It is not lawful for you to have her."*²⁶

Herodias was the granddaughter of Herod the Great and the daughter of his son Aristobulus IV. Herodias was married to her uncle Philip. Once Antipas, Philip's brother and Herod the Great's son, visited him and fell in love with Herodias. He persuaded Herodias to leave Herodias Phillips and marry him, so Herodias married his second uncle, Antipas.

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According to the Mosaic law, no man could marry his brother's widow while he was still alive, and if someone dared to do it, it would be considered as committing adultery.

*"Thou shalt not uncover the nakedness of thy brother's wife: it is thy brother's nakedness."*²⁷

*"If a man marries his brother's wife, it is impurity. He has violated the intimacy that belongs to his brother; they will be childless."*²⁸

On this shameful act, John the Baptist denounced Antipas, and Antipas put him in prison.

The husband of Salome III, the daughter of Herod the Great's third wife Mary II, was named Philip. But the evangelist says that Philip is the husband of Herodias, which is against the historical fact. Some commentators of the New Testament have tried to explain here that the family name of Herodias' husband Herod was Philip, but there is no solid evidence of this. To believe in this interpretation is nothing but self-delusion.

The most important thing in this whole matter is that Antipas married his niece, which was a very bad act from a moral and social point of view, but surprisingly, there is no such statement of Prophet John the Baptist in the Gospel in which he described this act as abominable. But Herod Antipas was reprimanded. On the contrary, they criticize the action of Antipas keeping his brother's wife while he was still alive, even though Antipas was an idolater who had nothing to do with the Mosaic Law. In such a situation, John the Baptist can't accuse a person of Shariah acts against someone who does not accept the Shariah. It is quite possible that Prophet John the Baptist reprimanded him for marrying his niece, whom the evangelists criticized for marrying his brother's wife. Looking at all these historical facts, Antipas has no justification for arresting and unjustly killing Prophet John the Baptist. The Jews may have done the injustice, but the evangelists gave it a different color. Other historical sources are silent about the martyrdom of Prophet Yahya (peace be upon him). Only the Testament is modern, which presents his oppressed martyrdom with a legendary color, but the historical status of this entire legend is very doubtful and innovative, due to which the Gospel narrative becomes unacceptable.

Ancient traditions about prophets' murder:

According to biblical and Rabbinic traditions, Prophet Zechariah was killed by Jehoash king, Uriah bin Shemaiah was killed by Jehoiakim, while Prophet Isaiah (a) was martyred on the orders of King Manasseh.²⁹ An ancient Christian book "*The Book of the Bee*" (1222 AD) mentions several prophets who were killed by the Jews. Prophet Micah was martyred by King Jehoram, and Amos was martyred by the priest of Bethel. In addition, Prophet Jeremiah was stoned by the leader of the Jews, Prophet Habakkuk was stoned by the Jews of Jerusalem and Prophet Ezekiel was martyred by the leader of the Jews in Babylon.

Chronicle of Palestinian massacres by Israelites:

It began with the 1948 massacres and expulsion of Palestinians, and it has continued for more than fifty years under military occupation, with frequent military attacks on Gaza and blatant declarations by the Israeli government endorsing the eradication of the Palestinian people. Historical reports indicate that at least 33 massacres and other random acts of violence against Palestinians were carried out during this chaotic time by both Israeli and Yishuv (later Israeli) soldiers.

Deir Yassin Massacre of Palestinians (April 1948)

In the Deir Yassin massacre, at least 107 Palestinians were killed. Numerous women, children, and senior citizens were among the victims.³⁰

On April 9, 1948, Zionist armed groups carried out a massacre in the Palestinian village of Deir Yassin, which lies close to Jerusalem. The Irgun and Stern Gang, commanded by Menachem Begin and Yitzhak Shamir, respectively, were responsible for the slaughter. Shamir and Begin both went on to become prime ministers of Israel. A few victims have been found dead after being raped and left mutilated. Whole families were killed. Thousands of men were loaded into trucks and paraded around Jerusalem before being executed in a quarry. The slaughter in Deir Yassin and the fear it instilled among Palestinians beyond their borders were essential in persuading the leaders of neighbouring Arab countries, who had been reluctant to interfere at first, to use force. This ultimately resulted in their engagement in the battle.³¹

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Tantura Massacre of Palestinian by Israelites (May 1948)

Tantura was a fishing community along the coast that had around 1,500 residents in 1945. It was located close to Haifa. The community gave itself over to Israeli forces in the 1948 Arab-Israeli War. But rather than a smooth transfer, the community was attacked by Israeli soldiers, which led to the terrible murder of about 200 Palestinians.

Village youths were ruthlessly slain and interred in group graves. Following an inquiry into this crime in the now-destroyed Palestinian hamlet, three potential mass graves located beneath a beach resort have been discovered.³²

Qibya Massacre of Palestinians by Israelites (October 1953)

Under Ariel Sharon's command, a group of 250–300 Israeli soldiers attacked the village of Qibya in the West Bank, which was now governed by Jordan. Palestinian civilians lost their lives as a result of this unfortunate incident. Over 69 Palestinian residents were massacred by Israeli soldiers after they used explosives to destroy dozens of structures throughout the town.³³ Women and children made up about two thirds of the deceased. In addition, 45 homes, a mosque, and a school were completely destroyed in the horrific attack.³⁴

Sabra and Shatila Massacres (September 1982)

The atrocities took place in the backdrop of the September 1982 Israeli invasion of Lebanon. The West Beirut refugee camps of Sabra and Shatila were encircled by Israeli soldiers. The right-wing Christian Phalangist militia, allied with Israel, was allowed admission into the camps by the Israeli troops. Between 16 and 18 September, the Phalangists carried out a heinous two-day operation that claimed the lives of almost 3,000 people in Lebanon and a significant number of Palestinian refugees. Both internationally and domestically, Israel was criticized for this atrocity.³⁵

Massacres in Gaza

Palestinian deaths from Israeli assaults in Gaza have been heavy:

Killing in 2008-2009: On December 27, 2008, Israel launched a massive military operation in the Gaza Strip, which marked the beginning of the Gaza Massacre. This came after a shaky six-month ceasefire between Israel and Hamas expired on December 19. The Israeli invasion

began with a heavy bombing of civilian infrastructure, including homes, schools, mosques, and medical institutions. White phosphorus weapons were often dropped from the air over inhabited areas by Israeli forces. The Israeli ground invasion began on January 3, 2009, and it is reported that between 1,166 and 1,417 Palestinians died as a consequence.³⁶

Killing in 2012: After a slew of killings by Israel in October 2012 that targeted Hamas officials, the organization retaliated by firing several missiles into Israeli territory. The assassinations of Mohamed Al-Hams and Ahmad Jabari, the deputy commander-in-chief of the *Ezzeddin Al-Qassam Brigades*, in November marked a significant uptick in Israel's assault on Gaza. Israeli strikes increased in intensity, resulting in 1,220 Palestinian injuries, including 430 children, and 165 Palestinian deaths, including 42 children.³⁷

Killing in 2014: An even more catastrophic Gaza War than the one that occurred in 2008–2009 broke out on July 8, 2014, and lasted for fifty days. Tensions with Gaza escalated as a result of Israeli reprisal strikes on Palestinians in East Jerusalem, which came after the kidnapping of three Israelis in the West Bank. Israel launched several airstrikes to start the hostilities. Since Hamas took over control of the Gaza Strip in 2007, this was Israel and Hamas' third major military clash. Following that, Israel invaded Gaza on foot, killing 2,205 Palestinians in the process.³⁸

Killing in 2021: Palestinians in East Jerusalem staged protests in response to the planned expulsion of six families from the Sheikh Jarrah neighborhood in occupied Jerusalem, which marked the beginning of the conflict. Over 600 people were reported injured when Israeli police forcibly invaded the Al-Aqsa Mosque compound on May 7 and used tear gas, rubber bullets, and stun grenades. This was the beginning of an escalating scenario. Israel launched hundreds of airstrikes after Hamas hit back by firing a barrage of rockets against the country. More than 300 Palestinians lost their life as a result of these airstrikes, half of whom were women and children. In addition, 1,948 people were injured, 400 of whom were women and 610 of whom were children.³⁹

Killing in 2023: Following a cross-border assault by the dominant Islamist party in the enclave, Hamas, on October 7, Israeli troops launched an aerial and ground blitz against the organization in Gaza. Since then, More than 22000 Palestinians have been martyred, according to data from the Gaza Health Ministry. Aid organizations caution that the

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humanitarian crisis in Gaza, where the majority of its 2.3 million residents are homeless and confined to a small, beleaguered coastal enclave with minimal access to fuel, food, water, medical treatment, and safe housing, is getting worse by the hour. The destruction of basic infrastructure, regular disruptions to phone and internet connections, and the deaths or disappearance of many health statisticians have raised fears that Gaza's health officials may not be able to maintain a reliable tally of the number of casualties.⁴⁰

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